

International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology

(A Peer Reviewed Online Journal)
Impact Factor: 5.164

Chief Editor
Dr. J.B. Helonde

Executive Editor
Mr. Somil Mayur Shah

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON THE MANAGEMENT
CAPABILITY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL HEADS IN AREA V-A, LEYTE
DIVISION****Maricar A. Cabodil**

School Principal, Department of Education, Leyte Division

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3632507

ABSTRACT

This study attempted to assess the emotional intelligence and the management capabilities of the elementary school heads in Area V-A, Leyte Division. Using the descriptive correlational design, there were 151 respondents composed of school administrators and teachers from the different elementary schools in the said division. The profile of the school heads showed that more than one-third of them were female; mostly were married; nearly one half of them were with MS or MA Units; Principal I topped their designation; and the highest number of trainings attended which they had attended was in the division level. The school heads showed high intelligence when it comes to interpersonal communication under stress. As to self-management in life and career, the school heads were viewed by the respondents very highly and positively. Intrapersonal development of the school heads' emotional state was somewhat average in intrapersonal valuing or in self-esteem. It was found out that the school heads had very high personal belief. They demonstrated very positive and high self-efficacy. Likewise, the school heads displayed also high and strong self-consciousness. As regards empathy, they fell in the average level as well. In terms of their management capabilities, the school heads were found to be very highly capable as well as competent in management of school goals, instructional management, direct supervision of instruction, accountable management and bureaucratic management. There were significant relationships between the socio-demographic profile of the school heads and school performance. Also, a significant relationship between school heads emotional intelligence and school performance existed. However, there was no significant relationship between the school heads' management capabilities and school performance. It was concluded that the emotional intelligence of the elementary school heads had impact to the school. Their management capabilities, however, had no bearing or influence to school performance. Similar studies may be conducted but should focus on other aspects or variables of emotional intelligence and management behavior and/or skills for the school heads to come up with genuine and adequate data as basis for other future research into this subject.

KEYWORDS: Emotional intelligence; management capability; school performance; school head; Leyte.**1. INTRODUCTION**

For more than three decades, researchers have postulated that emotional intelligence greatly complements an individual's ability to work collaboratively within a team setting, cope with stress, and lead others (Caruso & Salovey, 2004; George, 2000). For example, leaders who are unable to discern and self-assess their emotions may not recognize certain cues from their co-workers or subordinates. Likewise, administrators who display poor management over emotions may allow their emotions to interfere with their level of efficacy as it pertains to leading. For instance, when they feel anxious, they may avoid giving an important speech, or when they feel angry, they may inappropriately lash out at a co-worker.

Moreover, the rapid technological and post-modern advances in society have led some to suggest the competencies that previously constituted leadership effectiveness have changed markedly in the 21st century (Sternberg, 1996). In particular, Bass and Avolio (1990) noted that the work environment has become increasingly emotionally laden. Their findings coincide with the more general consensus that emotions are now a fundamental aspect of the contemporary workplace (Barsade, Brief, & Spataro, 2003) given the shift from a Weberian bureaucratic organization to a more organic customer-centered organization (Cascio, 2003).

Leadership scholars have also called for a better understanding of the dispositional traits that effect the way leaders evoke, frame and, mobilize emotions in the workplace (Ashford & Humphrey, 1995).

Both the concept and the term “emotional intelligence” (EI), have found their way into the contemporary theory and lexicon of both psychology and organizational behavior. Conceivably, a leader or manager with the ability to perceive, understand, and effectively manage and use emotions could significantly impact personal and organizational effectiveness. Furthermore, the awareness and cultivation of emotional intelligence, when viewed as an investment in human capital, could alter the manner in which organizations select, train, and place members within the organization, as well as reduce costs associated with human resource development.

In more recent research, Waters, Marzano, and McNulty (2003) have identified 21 specific leadership responsibilities that provide a concrete framework of responsibilities, practices, knowledge, strategies, tools, and resources that principals must accept in order to be effective school leaders. DeFranco and Golden (2003) developed a set of standards that specify the knowledge and skills necessary for school administrators. Goleman (1998) contends that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on leadership performance in organizations. Outstanding leaders are adept at using their emotional intelligence in moving their organizations forward (Goleman, Boyatzis, & McKee, 2002).

Emotional intelligence is a person’s ability to recognize personnel feelings and those of others and to manage emotions within themselves and in their relationships with others (Goleman, 1998).

Emotional intelligence significantly influences the performance of a leader (Cherniss & Goleman, 2001). A leader who has a high level of emotional intelligence will have a greater effect on an organization than a leader with a low level of emotional intelligence (Cherniss, 2003). Organizations are realizing that emotional intelligence is an essential part of an organization’s management process; and, with the current emphasis on team building and adapting to change, emotional intelligence becomes more critical (Goleman, 1998). If leaders expect to guide their organizations in the right directions, they need to be able to deal effectively with emotions. Great leaders have the ability to work through emotions (Goleman, Boyatzis, & McKee, 2002).

Researchers over the past decade have shown that in the business world a positive correlation exists between effective leaders and emotional intelligence (Caruso, & Salovey, 2004; Bradberry, & Greaves, 2003; Singh, 2003; Goleman, 1998). Individuals high in emotional intelligence tend to perform at a higher level than their counterparts with low emotional intelligence, and those who tend to improve or work on their emotional intelligence outperform cohorts who do not (Bradberry, & Greaves, 2003). Current research on emotional intelligence and leadership effectiveness supports the hypothesis that self-reported emotional intelligence is linked to transformational leadership style (Barling, Slater, & Kelloway, 2000; Gardner & Stough, 2002; Palmer, Walls, Burgess, & Stough, 2001). Barling et al. (2000) conducted an exploratory study on the relationship between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership. Their results suggest that self-reported emotional intelligence is associated with three aspects of transformational leadership, namely idealized influence, inspirational motivation, and individualized consideration. The leaders who report exhibiting these types of behaviors were assumed to be more effective in the workplace; however, no empirical research exists to refute or substantiate this assumption.

Being a school head, the researcher is challenged to bring this issue to the fore and to look into this aspect particularly in the division of Leyte where, as the current school principal in an elementary school, is located. Consequently, this study was pursued to establish first-hand data and information which will somehow capacitate the Department of Education to consider the real causes of certain educational problems and to primarily consider the role and position of the school heads. Results of this study is expected to draw the line in addressing the need among school heads to be within the purview of what is called as sound and well-balanced school management.

1.1 Objectives of the study

This study aimed to determine the role of emotional intelligence on the management capabilities of school heads in Area V-A Leyte Division.

Specifically, it sought to attain the following objectives:

1. Determine the profile of elementary school administrators in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 educational attainment;
 - 1.5 in-service training attended;
 - 1.6 official designation; and
 - 1.7 experience;
2. Assess the emotional intelligence of the elementary school heads in the following dimensions:
 - 2.1 intrapersonal communication under stress;
 - 2.2 self-management in life and career;
 - 2.3 intrapersonal development;
 - 2.4 personal belief;
 - 2.5 self-efficacy;
 - 2.6 self-consciousness; and
 - 2.7 empathy;
3. Determine the management capabilities of elementary school heads in terms of:
 - 3.1 management school goals;
 - 3.2 instructional management;
 - 3.3 direct supervision of instruction;
 - 3.4 accountable management;
 - 3.5 bureaucratic management; and
 - 3.6 education management
4. Determine the school performance of elementary schools in Area V-A Leyte Division;
5. Find out the significant relationship between the profile of the elementary school heads and their emotional intelligence;
6. Find out the significant relationship between the elementary school heads' emotional intelligence and their management capabilities;
7. Design a model to improve the management capabilities and emotional intelligence of school heads in Area V-A Leyte Division.

1.2 Framework of the study

Theoretical Framework. This study is based on the Emotional Intelligence Theory and Contingency/Situation Theory.

The roots of emotional intelligence can be traced back to E.L. Thorndike's (1920) identification of social intelligence. Thorndike's conceptualization of social intelligence is the ability to understand and manage people. Emotional intelligence as a subset of social intelligence whereby emotional intelligence involves the "ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions." After two decades of study and research, the science of emotional intelligence is still in its infancy stage. Researchers have not yet come to any consensus about how to conceptualize the construct of emotional intelligence. There has in fact been great amount of diversity surrounding the beliefs associated with emotional intelligence.

The Contingency/Situation Theory by Fiedler (1964) propounded that variations in leader effectiveness are predicted by individual differences in either trait or behavioral style. The theory offers an alternative to trait and behavioral style theories of leadership. His findings suggest that key features of a situation interact with leader's style to determine the level of effectiveness. Contingent theory posited that a leader's style is relatively static, reflecting established motivational and temperamental factors, but that some styles are more effective in some situations than others. Fiedler distinguished the following sorts of variations which determine how "favourable" a situation is, and which might account for different levels of leadership effectiveness: (A) Task Structure – the complexity of the job in terms of goal clarity, the degree to which correct solutions are obvious and the number of possible routes/solutions. (B) Position Power – the extent to which the organization

legitimizes the leader’s authority and confers formal/informal power. (C) Leader-Member Relations – the extent to which the leader has the acceptance, confidence, support and loyalty of subordinates.

Conceptual Framework. The schema in figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study

The schema of the conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive-correlational research design using the survey questionnaire in gathering the data. Aside from the questionnaires, a focus-group-discussion was conducted by the researcher to triangulate the data generated from the survey. The instruments were the survey questionnaires and focus-group-discussion (FGD). The survey questionnaire is a standardized tool lifted from Darwin B. Nelson and Gary R. Low (2011).

The study was conducted in Area V-A Leyte Division, which comprises the seven districts namely: Mac Arthur, Mayorga, Javier, Mahaplag, Abuyog North, Abuyog East, and Abuyog South. This was undertaken in the school year 2016-2017.

The respondents of this study were the one hundred four (104) school teachers throughout Area V-A Leyte Division. Additionally, there were another forty-seven (47) elementary school heads from the area of which the total sample population was taken through the use of random sampling. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, counts percentage and mean were used.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the statistical data and the respective implications concerning the emotional intelligence and management capability of the elementary school heads in Area V-A, Leyte Division.

Profile of the Elementary School Heads

Table 1 shows the profile of the elementary school heads in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, in-service training attended, official designation and experience.

Table 1

*Profile of Elementary School Heads
(age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and official designation)*

	f	%
<i>Age</i>		
60 and above (senior citizen)	2	4.30
46 to 59 (old age)	25	53.20
22 to 45 (middle age)	20	42.60
Total	47	100
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	12	25.50
Female	35	74.50
Total	47	100
<i>Civil Status</i>		
Single	8	17.00
Married	36	76.60
Widow / Widower	3	6.40
Total	47	100
<i>Educational Attainment</i>		
Ph.D / Ed.D.	4	8.50
Ph.D / Ed.D Units	11	23.40
MS / MA	10	21.30
MS / MA Units	22	46.80
Total	47	100
<i>Official Designation</i>		
Principal II	4	8.50
Principal I	16	34.00
Head Teacher III	5	10.60
Head Teacher I	8	17.00
Teacher-in-Charge	14	29.80
Total	47	100

Age. It can be seen on the table that more than half of the respondents with a frequency of 25 or 53.20 percent belonged to old age while a little nearly one half with a frequency of 20 or 42.60 percent were middle age. Only 2 or 4.30 percent were senior citizens. The data denotes that the bigger number of school heads were middle age

and would imply that in 5-10 years' time the schools in Area V-a would have shortage of teachers as many of these teachers would be retiring then. Bii, Lucas, Mwengi et al. (2012) investigated the relationship between age and EI of managers and whether the relationship is moderated by gender and managerial experience in educational institutions including primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. They observed that age had a positive and significant influence on EI and moderating effects of gender and managerial experience were mild and non-significant.

Sex. As gleaned in the table, more than one-third of the respondents were female with a frequency of 35 or 74.50 percent while the male respondents were few with a frequency of 12 or 25.50 percent. The female elementary school heads outnumbered the male ones. The findings of Cliffe (2011) indicate that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and female leadership. The findings imply that female school principals can control their emotions. There are studies that have been conducted investigating the difference between the emotional intelligence of male and female leaders. Some scholars found women leaders to be more emotionally intelligent than men leaders while others found no difference between men and women leaders' emotional intelligence.

Civil status. Mostly of the respondents were married with a frequency of 36 or 76.60 percent. Next were the singles with a frequency of 8 or 17 percent. The least were the widow/widowers with a frequency of 3 or 6.40 percent. This indicates that despite having families to look after they were still able to carry out their duties and responsibilities being school heads.

Educational attainment. Nearly one half of the school heads with a frequency of 22 or 46.80 percent were with MS or MA Units. Second in rank were those with Ph.D./Ed.D. units with a frequency of 11 or 23.40 percent. There were only four or 8.50 percent with Ph.D. or Ed.D. degrees. The data goes to show that many of the school heads still need to expand their educational opportunities and graduate educational experiences to reach the peak of their professional career and be equipped with new knowledge, ideas and theories in improving their leadership and management skills and capabilities.

Official designation. Principal I topped the designation with a frequency of 16 or 34 percent of the respondents. There were also teacher-in-charge with a frequency of 14 or 29.80 percent which is second. The rest which is less in number were Head teachers and Principal II. The big number of the Principal designation is higher because the main respondents selected in the study were school heads.

Table 2				
<i>Profile of Elementary School Heads (age, in-service trainings attended, and length of work experience)</i>				
	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Age	32	63	46.17	8.646
INSET Division	1	47	11.24	8.761
INSET Regional	0	20	4.87	3.816
INSET National	0	4	1.00	1.022
INSET Overall	2	51	16.55	11.645
Length of Work Experience	1	33	19.43	8.519

In-service trainings attended. The highest number of trainings attended by the respondents was division level with a mean of 11.24 percent; regional level was in the second spot with 4.87 percent; and last was national level with only 1 percent. The result connotes that the school heads have rarely attended trainings related to their position and work. From the findings, it can be implied that the school heads may have insufficient knowledge and competencies on new management theories and perspectives given their present scenario and conditions.

Emotional Intelligence of the School Heads

A major objective which would give meaning to the present study was the assessment of the emotional intelligence of the school heads. This was achieved by specifically measuring the elements on interpersonal communication under stress, self-management in life and career, intrapersonal development, personal belief, self-efficacy, self-consciousness, and empathy. These are presented in the following tables with corresponding discussions.

Table 4

Interpersonal Communication Under Stress of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
I usually feel some tension but comfortable in expressing exactly what is on my mind.	4.28	0.713	Agree
I usually think "Okay", I'm angry and need to deal with it constructively.	4.19	0.741	Agree
I usually behave by expressing what is bothering me, and working to achieve a constructive resolution.	4.28	0.743	Agree
I usually feel tension and the right to understand the person's anger by responding directly.	4.26	0.793	Agree
I usually behave comfortably and at ease with the person.	4.30	0.689	Strongly Agree
I am confident in my ability to be comfortable and effective in communicating with other people.	4.36	0.640	Strongly Agree
I am comfortable with all kinds of people.	4.26	0.793	Agree
My relationships with others are smooth and comfortable.	4.34	0.668	Strongly Agree
I can tell how friendly I can be with a stranger.	4.32	0.810	Strongly Agree
My voice is variable and clear, and I am easily heard by others.	4.28	0.713	Agree
I know when it is okay for me to put my hand on another person's shoulder.	4.36	0.735	Strongly Agree
I listen to and really understand another person's feelings.	4.38	0.709	Strongly Agree
I am the kind of person that people are really able to talk to about personal problems.	4.34	0.731	Strongly Agree
My friends tell me that I am an understanding person.	4.45	0.717	Strongly Agree
I understand and am patient with someone who is experiencing a lot of emotions.	4.43	0.683	Strongly Agree
I am a caring person, and people seem to sense this in me.	4.34	0.731	Strongly Agree
I accurately feel what another person feels.	4.40	0.614	Strongly Agree
I am a good decision maker.	4.23	0.666	Agree
My decisions are usually accepted as "good" by the persons affected.	4.21	0.623	Agree
When faced with an important decision, I am not overly anxious about making a wrong choice.	4.17	0.702	Agree
My friends and co-workers ask me for help in making important decisions.	4.30	0.805	Strongly Agree
I make a decision and act rather than worrying about the alternatives and becoming tense.	4.26	0.846	Agree
I follow an established process that guides me in making important decisions.	4.26	0.820	Agree
I have a good ability to help others solve problems.	4.28	0.713	Agree
When a group that I am in needs a spokesperson, I am usually elected.	4.11	0.787	Agree
I am a good leader.	4.17	0.842	Agree
I "take charge" of a situation when I need to.	4.28	0.772	Agree

When I really feel strongly about something, I am influential in gaining agreement in a group.	4.19	0.770	Agree
I feel comfortable about approaching another person with the idea of selling him/her something	4.23	0.786	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.28		Agree

Interpersonal communication under stress. It can be observed that the school heads showed high intelligence when it comes to interpersonal communication under stress as evident of the general weighted mean of 4.28 described as “Agree”. Among the given 29 indicators, 12 were strongly agreed by the respondents and the other 17 were agreed by them.

The indicator “*My friends tell me that I am an understanding person*” obtained the highest mean of 4.45 described as “Strongly Agree” while the indicator “*When a group that I am in needs a spokesperson, I am usually elected*” obtained the lowest mean of 4.11 described as “Agree”. This area speaks of the tendency and ability of the school heads to relate and connect with other people especially those she/she is working with which relates to his/her being emotional intelligent when it comes to interpersonal communication under stress. This would imply that the school heads have good or positive working relationships with their workforce which could lead to the attainment of organizational goals. This aspect of interpersonal ability is highly needed for a school head to act wisely in human relationships (Nelson & Low, 2011). The emotional intelligence scale identified in this competency is assertion; it involves effective communication, emotional self-control, and understanding and appreciating differences in others. According to Gragg (2008), having self-control reinforces the values that are identified through a self-awareness of emotions which include understanding and responding to one’s own emotions. An important idea concerning self-control is that leaders cannot effectively manage emotions in others without first handling their own emotions; therefore, they themselves must stay calm and clear headed under stress or during crisis (Goleman et al., 2002).

Table 5

Self-Management in Life and Career of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
I set priorities and meet objectives effectively	4.30	0.657	Strongly Agree
When I begin a difficult task, I am motivated more by the thought of success than by the thought of failure	4.40	0.712	Strongly Agree
I feel that my present work is satisfying	4.43	0.715	Strongly Agree
I have more than enough energy to get me through the day	4.38	0.739	Strongly Agree
I have a strong desire to be a success in the things that I set out to do	4.32	0.837	Strongly Agree
I set daily goals for myself.	4.43	0.715	Strongly Agree
I am an efficient and well organized person.	4.32	0.663	Strongly Agree
I plan and complete my work of schedule.	4.28	0.682	Agree
I set objectives for myself and then successfully complete them within a specific time frame.	4.26	0.765	Agree
I control my responsibilities rather than being controlled by being.	4.38	0.739	Strongly Agree
I effectively work on several projects on the same time with good results.	4.26	0.642	Agree
I waste very little time.	4.23	0.786	Agree
People admire my ability to accomplish what I set out to do.	4.30	0.623	Strongly Agree
Even when I encounter personal difficulties, I complete assignments and obligations	4.40	0.681	Strongly Agree
In almost in any area that I go into, I really do well.	4.28	0.649	Agree
I rarely fail at anything that I consider important.	4.30	0.778	Strongly Agree

I have a solid feeling of confidence in my ability to create a good life for myself	4.36	0.705	Strongly Agree
I am considered a dependable person	4.40	0.681	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.33		Strongly Agree

Self-management in life and career. This aspect of the emotional intelligence of the school heads were viewed by them very highly and positively as reflected by their response of “Strongly Agree” which garnered a weighted mean of 4.33. Among the 16 indicators, 13 were strongly agreed by the respondents and the other three were agreed by them. The indicator “*I feel that my present work is satisfying*” got the highest weighted mean of 4.40 which means strongly agreed by the school administrators while the indicator “*I waste very little time*” got the lowest average weighted mean of 4.20 which means agreed by them. Despite the extremity among the variables, still the self-management in life and career of the respondents was so favorable and highly positive to them. The findings cited here implies both the inclination and firm resolve of the school heads to do things pertaining to their life and career in affirmative and optimistic perspectives which means they are able to succeed both in family life and career. This implies as well their being emotionally intelligent in these areas. This finding is congruent to the findings of the study on self-management competency setting and meeting meaningful goals, managing time and resources, and learning to be flexible when unexpected demands or changes arise (Nelson &Low, 2011). Further, Goleman et al. (2002) stated that an important idea with self-management is that leaders cannot effectively manage emotions in others without first handling their own emotions. Leaders who have mastered their own emotions are better able to cope with changes and help organizations adjust.

Table 6

<i>Intrapersonal Development of School Heads</i>			
	Mean	SD	Description
I trust my ability to size up the situation.	4.32	0.837	Strongly Agree
I am excited about myself and the potential that I have to develop as a person.	4.26	0.820	Agree
I feel in control of my life.	4.30	0.858	Strongly Agree
I am an open, honest, and spontaneous person.	4.43	0.683	Strongly Agree
I like myself, and I feel very comfortable with the way I am as a person.	4.43	0.715	Strongly Agree
For me, anything is possible if I believe in myself.	4.40	0.648	Strongly Agree
Even when I try to enjoy myself and relax, I feel a lot of pressure	4.21	0.778	Agree
My friends often say that I look worried, tense or uptight.	4.02	0.847	Agree
I have become extremely nervous and tense at times and doctors have advised me to slow down and relax.	3.89	1.088	Agree
I am impatient with myself and others, and I am usually	3.83	1.070	Agree
I often feel that I have little control over what I think, feel and do.	4.00	1.083	Agree
I feel tense and pressured by the way I have to live.	3.91	1.060	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.17		Agree

Intrapersonal development. As regard this component of the school heads’ emotional state, this was rated by them “Agree” with an average weighted mean of 4.17 which attributes to the respondents’ somewhat average intrapersonal valuing or self-esteem as evident in some of the indicators contained in the table. Over all, the indicators “*I am an open, honest, and spontaneous person*” and “*I like myself, and I feel very comfortable with the way I am as a person*” were strongly agreed by the school heads with weighted means of 4.40, respectively. In contrast, indicators “*I have become extremely nervous and tense at times and doctors have advised me to slow down and relax*” and “*I am impatient with myself and others, and I am usually*” gained lower weighted means of 3.83 and 3.89 which are indicative of the pessimism towards themselves. Evidently, these findings show the school heads’ average emotional intelligence in terms of their intra personal development. Corollary to

this, it can be implied that the respondents don't feel good about themselves and lack confidence in some ways which can also impede them from doing the best they could relative to their jobs and responsibilities.

This is confirmed by Nelson and Low (2011) who defined intrapersonal competency as an awareness of the perception, value, and betterment of one's self as well as dealing with demands, stresses, and pressures of life. Identifying and capitalizing on one's strengths help promote a positive self-esteem and increases a person's optimism and self-worth. In a study by Blase and Kirby (2000), optimism was identified as a critical component for effective leadership. They submitted that the leader sets the emotional tone for good or worse within the organization.

Table 7

Personal Belief of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
I have a good sense of why I have certain feelings most of the time.	4.19	0.770	Agree
I have a good understanding of my own emotions.	4.32	0.726	Strongly Agree
I really understand what I feel.	4.36	0.705	Strongly Agree
I always know whether or not I am happy.	4.45	0.717	Strongly Agree
I always my friends' emotion from their behavior	4.36	0.640	Strongly Agree
I am a good observer of others' emotions.	4.28	0.772	Agree
I am sensitive to the feelings and emotions of others.	4.30	0.657	Strongly Agree
I have good understanding of the emotions of people around me.	4.28	0.682	Agree
I always set goals for myself then try my best to achieve them.	4.38	0.677	Strongly Agree
I always tell myself I am a competent person.	4.32	0.594	Strongly Agree
I am self-motivated person.	4.32	0.726	Strongly Agree
I would always encourage myself to try my best.	4.19	0.798	Agree
I am able to control my anger and handle difficulties rationally.	4.32	0.810	Strongly Agree
I am quite capable of controlling my emotions.	4.28	0.772	Agree
I can always calm down quickly when I am angry. I have good control of my own emotions	4.40	0.712	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.32		Strongly Agree

Personal belief. It was found out that this element of emotional intelligence was strongly agreed by the respondents as seen in the weighted mean of 4.32. Among the 15 identified indicators, 10 were strongly agreed by the respondents and 5 others were only agreed by them. The indicator "I always know whether or not I am happy" obtained the highest mean of 4.45 described as "Strongly Agree" while the indicator "I have a good sense of why I have certain feelings most of the time." obtained the lowest mean of 4.19 described as "Agree". Although a slight difference among the indicators could be pointed out, personal belief of school heads was very high for them which mean that they always look at the bright side or positive view of things especially on what they do. This displays the respondents favorable and nurturing disposition in life which implies that, much as they want things to be in proper perspective for themselves, it is also very likely that they contextualize their functions and responsibilities in the same manner. Thus, this further implies that the respondents are able to do better and contribute to the development of the organizations they are in.

Table 8

Self-Efficacy of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
I will be able to achieve most of the goals I have set for	4.34	0.635	Strongly Agree

myself			
When facing difficult task, I am certain I will achieve them.	4.34	0.668	Strongly Agree
In general, I think I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.	4.36	0.605	Strongly Agree
I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind.	4.40	0.712	Strongly Agree
I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges	4.28	0.772	Agree
I am confident I can perform effectively on my task	4.28	0.800	Agree
Compared to other people, I can do most task very well.	4.21	0.778	Agree
Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well.	4.23	0.840	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.31		Strongly Agree

Self-efficacy. This component of the school heads' emotional intelligence was answered by them "Strongly Agree" through the weighted mean of 4.31. All the indicators were split into two groups, one for "strongly agree" and the other one for "agree". Specifically, the indicator "I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind" attained the highest weighted mean of 4.40 while the indicator "Compared to other people, I can do most task very well" had the lowest frequency of 4.21. Despite the slight difference among the given indicators, they still attributed to the very positive and high self-efficacy of the respondents which translates to the school heads ability to succeed in specific situations or accomplish a task. This also implies that they were able to assume major roles on how one approaches goals, tasks, and challenges.

Table 9

Self-Consciousness of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
I am always trying to figure myself out	4.26	0.765	Agree
Generally, I am not very aware of myself.	3.87	1.115	Agree
I am often the subject of my own fantasies.	4.04	0.932	Agree
I never scrutinized myself.	4.06	0.919	Agree
I am generally attentive to my inner feelings.	4.30	0.657	Strongly Agree
I sometimes have the feeling that I am off somewhere watching myself.	4.13	0.797	Agree
I am alert to changes in my mood.	4.17	0.816	Agree
I am aware of the way my mind works when I work through a problem.	4.28	0.713	Agree
I reflect about myself a lot.	4.36	0.673	Strongly Agree
I am constantly examining my motives.	4.19	0.770	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.17		Agree

Self-consciousness. The emotional intelligence of the school heads in terms of self-consciousness got an average weighted mean of 4.17 described as "Agree". From the listed indicators, two came out very highly which are "I am generally attentive to my inner feelings" and "I reflect about myself a lot", both strongly agreed by the respondents. Meanwhile, the indicator "I am constantly examining my motives" had the lowest mean of 4.19 rated as agreed. The data reveals that the school heads displayed high and strong self-consciousness which translates to their greater sensitivity to what they feel relative to their actions or deeds. From this finding, implication can be drawn that the school heads are in their usual good selves which is the key ingredient to be both perceptive and receptive in their roles as managers and leaders in their respective schools and organizations.

Table 10

<i>Empathy of School Heads</i>			
	Mean	SD	Description
I often tender concern feelings for people less fortunate than me.	4.43	0.744	Strongly Agree
I often have tender, concerned feelings for people less fortunate than me.	4.43	0.683	Strongly Agree
Sometimes, I don't feel very sorry for other people when they are having problem.	4.00	0.909	Agree
When I see someone being taken advantage of, I feel kind of protective towards them.	4.32	0.695	Strongly Agree
Other peoples' misfortune do not usually disturb me a great deal.	4.00	0.933	Agree
When I see someone treated unfairly, I sometimes don't feel much very pity for them.	3.87	1.135	Agree
I would describe myself as a pretty soft hearted person	4.28	0.649	Agree
	Weighted Mean	4.19	Agree

Empathy. As regards empathy, the school heads were marked with an average weighted mean of 4.19 regarded as “Agree”. Out of seven indicators, three were noted “Strongly Agree” by the respondents and four were marked by them as “Agree”. Indicators “I often tender concern feelings for people less fortunate than me” and “I often have tender, concerned feelings for people less fortunate than me” obtained the highest weighted means of 4.43s. However, the indicator “When I see someone treated unfairly, I sometimes don't feel much very pity for them” got the lowest mean of 3.87. The results divulge that the school heads have good empathy. Although the way the respondents perceived empathy is somewhat inconsistent, it can be said that they have the tendency to be more emphatic when confronted with specific situations directly or they are personally involved with it. On the other hand, their empathy is not so emergent when it is being placed in situations on others without the respondents being directly involved.

This shows that the school heads consider and value other people or individuals when they are directly attached to them which could draw an implication that they exhibit empathy trait when they are in real settings. Further, this would also imply that the school heads tend to demonstrate empathy at work only in actual situations they are likely part in or with.

Management Capabilities of School Heads

One of the major objectives of the study is the management capabilities of the school heads. To figure out data on this variable, several factors were examined which include management of school goals, instructional management, direct supervision of instruction, accountable management, and bureaucratic management. Data are provided in the following tables with narrative and descriptive presentations.

Table 11

<i>Management of School Goals of School Heads</i>			
	Mean	SD	Description
Makes sure that the professional development activities of teachers are in accordance with the teaching goals of the school.	4.47	0.396	Very Much Capable
Ensures that teachers work according to the schools' educational goals.	4.60	0.412	Very Much Capable
Use students' performance results to develop the school's educational goals.	4.57	0.403	Very Much Capable
Takes exam results into account in decisions regarding	4.51	0.483	Very Much

curriculum development			Capable
Ensures that there is clarity concerning the responsibilities for coordinating the curriculum.	4.48	0.489	Very Much Capable
	Weighted Mean	4.53	Very Much Capable

Management of school goals. As assessed by the respondents, this component generated a weighted mean of 4.53 described as “Very Much Capable”. All of the indicators were rated “Very Much Capable”. Interestingly, the indicator “Ensures that teachers work according to the schools' educational goals” got the highest weighted mean while the indicator “Makes sure that the professional development activities of teachers are in accordance with the teaching goals of the school” had the lowest. From the presented data, however, it is obvious that the school heads had performed very well their roles and management functions as assessed by the teachers. This would mean that the school heads are very much concerned and dedicated to achieving the school goals and they are after the success and development of their respective schools.

Table 12

<i>Instructional Managements of School Heads</i>			
	Mean	SD	Description
Takes the initiative to discuss matters when a teacher has problems in his/her classroom.	4.39	0.429	Very Much Capable
Informs teachers about possibilities for updating their knowledge and skills.	4.48	0.477	Very Much Capable
Solves problems when a teacher brings up a classroom problem.	4.61	0.403	Very Much Capable
Pays attention to disruptive behavior in a classroom	4.49	0.505	Very Much Capable
	Weighted Mean	4.49	Very Much Capable

Instructional management. When it comes to this criterion, the school heads exhibited that they are “Very Much Capable” as indicative of the average weighted mean of 4.49. The prevalent indicator was “Pays attention to disruptive behavior in a classroom” with a weighted mean of 4.49. Meanwhile, the indicator “Takes the initiative to discuss matters when a teacher has problems in his/her classroom” attained the lowest mean of 4.39. It can be inferred from these findings that the school heads had proven their capability and competence in managing instruction. This implies that the respondents are versatile and well-rounded that they do not excel only in administrative aspect but also in instruction.

Table 13

<i>Direct Supervision of Instruction of School Heads</i>			
	Mean	SD	Description
Observes instructions in classrooms	4.66	0.363	Very Much Capable
Gives teachers suggestions as to how they can improve their teaching.	4.57	0.376	Very Much Capable
Monitors students work	4.52	0.442	Very Much Capable
Check to see whether classroom activities are keeping with our educational goals.	4.56	0.412	Very Much Capable
	Weighted Mean	4.58	Very Much Capable

Direct supervision of instruction. As gleaned from the table, the school heads were rated by their teachers “Very Much Capable” as depicted by the weighted mean of 4.58. Among the given indicators, “Observes instructions in classrooms” achieved the highest mean of 4.66 while the indicator “Monitors students work” got the lowest mean of 4.52. These results articulate the competence of the school heads being very much capable in directly supervising instruction which describes how seriously committed they are in monitoring and evaluating teachers to make sure that instruction is being prioritized. This finding would imply that the schools would be able to raise or improve its performance in instruction being one of the major deliverables of the school heads.

Table 14

Accountable Management of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
Ensures the school approved instructional approaches are explained to new teachers that more experienced teachers are using these approaches	4.51	0.383	Very Much Capable
Ensures that the teaching skills of the staff are always improving.	4.55	0.433	Very Much Capable
Ensures that teachers are held accountable for the attainment of school goals.	4.51	0.397	Very Much Capable
Present new ideas to the parents in a convincing way.	4.53	0.435	Very Much Capable
Weighted Mean	4.53		Very Much Capable

Accountable management. As indicated in the table, the school heads were rated by their teachers “Very Much Capable” in accountable management with an average weighted mean of 4.53. Among the given indicators, “Observes instructions in classrooms” achieved the highest mean of 4.66 while the indicator “Monitors students work” got the lowest mean of 4.52. These results articulate the competence of the school heads being very much capable in directly supervising instruction which describes how seriously committed they are in monitoring and evaluating teachers to make sure that instruction is being prioritized. This finding would imply that the schools would be able to raise or improve its performance with instruction being one of the major deliverables of the school heads.

Table 15

Bureaucratic Management of School Heads

	Mean	SD	Description
It is important for the school that the school head see to it that everyone sticks to the rules.	4.52	0.389	Very Much Capable
It is important for the school that the school head checks for mistakes and errors in administrative procedures and reports.	4.55	0.457	Very Much Capable
Resolves problems with the time table and/or lesson planning.	4.52	0.489	Very Much Capable
Creates an orderly atmosphere in the school.	4.55	0.393	Very Much Capable
Stimulates a task oriented atmosphere in the school	4.61	0.375	Very Much Capable
Weighted Mean	4.55		Very Much Capable

Bureaucratic management. As illustrated in the table, the school heads were “Very Much Capable” in bureaucratic management which got an average weighted mean of 4.55. The indicator “I” ranked first with a weighted mean of 4.61 and the indicators “Resolves problems with the time table and/or lesson planning” and

“It is important for the school that the school head checks for mistakes and errors in administrative procedures and reports” and “Resolves problems with the time table and/or lesson planning” were the lowest in weighted means at 4.52 for both. The data disclose that the school heads are very much skilled and competent in bureaucratic management. This goes to show that they always care to put the organization in its proper order and context. Obviously, this implies that the school heads have desired for the schools to adhere to the norms and noteworthy practices within the bounds of law.

School Performance of Elementary Schools in Area V-A Leyte Division

The school performance was taken as secondary data covering the last four years of the selected school-respondents.

Table 16

School Performance of Elementary Schools in Area V-A Leyte Division

S.Y.	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Median
2011-2012	75.90	3.953	68.37	81.67	76.40
2012-2013	77.18	3.666	70.68	82.27	77.66
2013-2014	80.35	3.157	75.12	85.97	80.75
2014-2015	80.09	3.269	73.05	84.814	80.21
Weighted Mean	78.38				

As contained in the table, the pattern of the school performance from school year 2011-2012 to school year 2014-2015 were increasing, although the last two consecutive school years there was a slightly low difference, as seen from 80.35 in school year 2013-2014 to 80.09 in school year 2014-2015. This data highlight the performance of the school heads as well which highlights how their emotional intelligence and management capabilities could be influential factors to what they achieve and for their respective schools.

The strong link between the emotional intelligence of the school heads and the school performance can never be ignored as evident in findings from some studies conducted. Ayiro (2009) also found positive results between emotional intelligence and school principals in the African context. Ayiro (2009) conducted a study in Kenya investigating the relationship between school principals’ emotional intelligence and their school performance. The participants were 100 high school principals from different regions around Kenya. The researcher categorized school as either high performing or low performing based on the examination results of the school. The findings of this study showed the importance of emotional intelligence for school leaders. The findings also showed a positive relationship.

Relationship of Variables

The relationships of variables were tested to find out whether there was or no significant relationship that existed among the variables identified. There are presented in the following tables.

Table 20

Relationship between Profile of Elementary School Heads and School Performance

Variables	p-value	r-value	Decision
Age	0.672	-0.063	Failed to Reject H ₀₁
Sex	0.701	0.058	Failed to Reject H ₀₁
Civil Status	0.690	-0.060	Failed to Reject H ₀₁
Highest Educational Attainment	0.891	0.021	Failed to Reject H ₀₁
In-Service Trainings Attended	0.188	0.196	Failed to Reject H ₀₁

Official Designation	0.553	0.089	Failed to Reject H ₀₁
No. of Years of Work Experience	0.838	-0.032	Failed to Reject H ₀₁

As presented in the table for the significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile of school heads and school performance using the significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The computed p-values for age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, in-service trainings attended, official designation and number of years of work experience were greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. The hypothesis failed to reject and therefore significant relationships existed. This means that the age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, in-service trainings attended, official designation and number of years of work experience of the school heads had affected or influenced their performance.

Table 21

Relationship between Elementary School Heads' Emotional Intelligence and School Performance

Variables		p-value	r-value	Decision
Elementary School Heads' Emotional Intelligence	School Performance	0.927	-0.014	Failed to Reject H ₀₂

As shown in the table, a significant relationship between the school heads' emotional intelligence and school performance was observed at $\alpha = 0.05$. level of significance. The computed p-values of 0.927 was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. The hypothesis failed to reject and therefore significant relationship existed. This means that the emotional intelligence of the school heads had affected or influenced their school performance.

Table 22

Relationship between Elementary School Heads' Management Capabilities and School Performance

Variables		p-value	r-value	Decision
Elementary School Heads' Management Capabilities	School Performance	0.010	0.884	Reject H₀₃

As disclosed in the table, there was no significant relationship between the school heads' management capabilities and school performance as evident in the computed p-value of 0.010 which was lower than $\alpha = 0.05$. The hypothesis was rejected and therefore there was no significant relationship between these variables. This means that the school heads' management capabilities had not affected or influenced school performance.

2. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS**Conclusion**

After intensive analysis and assessment of the findings and observations from the previous chapters, the researcher concluded that the emotional intelligence of the elementary school heads has an impact or can greatly affect the school performance whereby emotionally intelligent school managers/leaders would eventually help improve or increase school performance and this is inversely proportional as well.

The qualities and traits of the school heads indeed have strong bearing to their performance and therefore the better the profile characteristics of the leader/manager are, the competent he/she will become to the job.

The result that the management capabilities of the school had no bearing or influence to the school performance could be a possibility as management and leadership do not necessarily be the only single factor that could redound to good performance.

Recommendations

From the conclusions lifted through the findings and results in the previous chapters, the following recommendations are given:

- Emotional intelligence has a positive impact on leadership therefore being emotionally intelligent should be a criterion for appointment to school head position. At the appointment stage of school principals, candidates should be tested for emotional intelligence. If a person fails the emotional intelligence tests then he/she should not be appointed as a school principal because research has proven that emotional intelligence plays a significant role in the performance of a leader.
- All school principals should be trained on how to control their emotions and also how to manage the emotions of people they lead. This means that workshops for school principals should include sessions where school principals are equipped with emotional intelligence skills. A number of researchers have also recommended that workshops and trainings of school principals must include programs that will develop school principal's emotional intelligence skills.
- There are no specific strategies given to school principals on how they should manage their emotions. The Department of Education should investigate effective strategies for managing emotions for school leaders and document them. All school principals should then be given this document from the Department of Education where different strategies that they could use in managing their emotions are written.
- There should be sessions where school principals come together and share different strategies that they use in their respective schools to managing their emotions and those of others. These sessions could be organized in different Professional Learning Communities (PLC's) where a manageable number of school principals meet for discussion.
- Since having good relations at school results in good functionality of the school, School principals continuously ensure that there are activities organized that bring educators and other non-teaching staff members together so as to promote good relations. School principals should at all times promote teamwork where teachers work together in executing different duties, planning together, team teaching since this promotes good relations among educators.
- The Department of Education in Leyte Division should conduct more trainings and seminars on emotional intelligence and school management to further enhance the knowhow, expertise and competence of the school heads on this subject.
- There is a great need among the school heads to conduct school-wide teacher training program specifically on emotional intelligence so that the teachers will also become aware and adept about how their emotions work for them in relation to their teaching job.
- An emotional intelligence assessment tool maybe designed and crafted which will be used in determining the emotional intelligence of both the school heads and teachers which could be part of the criteria or requirement during the screening of job applicants.
- Teambuilding activities should also be conducted between the school heads and the teachers every now and then (maybe once every semester or twice a year) to expand better relationship management.
- The school heads may also either take courses/classes in management or attend seminars/trainings in this area to acquire more inputs on management of school and empower them as school leaders.
- Similar studies may be conducted but will examine other aspects and nature of variables on emotional intelligence and management behavior and/or skills for the school heads to come up with genuine and adequate data as basis for other future research into this subject.

REFERENCES

- [1] Arond-Thomas, M. (2003). EQ, not IQ, is the key to outstanding leadership performance. Retrieved April 10, 2007, from <http://www.indian-model.net/directory/culture>.
- [2] Ayiro, L.P. (2009). An Analysis of Emotional Intelligence and the Performance of Principals in Selected Schools in Kenya. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 11(6), 719-746.

- [3] Baltazar, Jose D. et. al. (2004). Management in the Philippine setting, National Book Store
- [4] Barling, J., Slater, F., & Kelloway, K. (2000). Transformational leadership and emotional intelligence: An exploratory study. *Leadership & Organizational Development Journal*, 21(3), 157-161.
- [5] Bii, P.K., Lucas, O., B.Mwengei, O. K., Koskey, N., Korir, E., & Yano, E.M. (2012). Age: a determinant of management's emotional intelligence competency. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)*, 3(6), 807-811. Retrieved April 20, 2014, from <http://jeteraps.scholarlinkresearch.org/abstractview.php?id=650>
- Blasé, J. (2001). *Empowering teachers: What successful principals do* (2nd Ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- [6] Blase, J. & Kirby, P. C. (2000). *Bringing out the best in teachers: What effective principals do* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- [7] Bradberry, T. & Greaves, J. (2003). *Emotional intelligence quickbook: Everything you need to know*, San Diego, CA: Talent Smart Inc.
- [8] Burbach, M. E. (2004). Testing the relationship between emotional intelligence and full-range leadership as moderated by cognitive style and self-concept. Unpublished dissertation, University of Nebraska, Lincoln.
- [9] Byron, K. L. (2003). Are better managers better at 'reading' others? Testing the claim that emotional intelligence predicts managerial performance. Unpublished dissertation, Georgia State University.
- [10] Caruso, D. R., & Salovey, P. (2004). *The emotionally intelligent manager: How to develop and use the four key emotional skills of leadership*, San Francisco, CA: Josey-Bass.
- [11] Cavallo, K. & Brienza, D. (n.d.). Emotional competence and leadership excellence at Johnson & Johnson: The emotional intelligence and leadership study. Retrieved February 18, 2006, from http://www.eiconsortium.org/research/jj_ei_study.htm.
- [12] Cherniss, C. (2003). The business case for emotional intelligence, The Consortium for Research on Emotional Intelligence in Organizations, Retrieved November 8, 2003, from http://www.eiconsortium.org/research/business_case_for_ei.htm.
- [13] Cherniss, C. & Goleman, D. (2001). *The emotionally intelligent workplace*. San Francisco, CA: Josey-Bass.
- [14] Collins, J. (2001). *Good to great: Why companies make the leap and others don't*. New York: HarperCollins.
- [15] Cotton, K. (2003). *Principals and student achievement: What research says*. Alexandre VA Associates for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- [16] Darling, Hammond (2004). Standards accountability and school reform. *Teacher college record*.
- [17] DeFranco, J. A. & Golden, N.L. (2003). *Educational leadership improvement tool: A research-based assessment, evaluation, & improvement tool for school administrators*. Eugene, OR: Eugene School District.
- [18] Gardner, L., & Stough, C. (2002). Examining the relationship between leadership and emotional intelligence in senior level managers. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 23(2), 68-78.
- [19] Gardner, H. (1983,1993). *Frames of mind: The theory of multiple intelligences* (Rev. ed.). New York: Basic Books.
- [20] Elmor, Ruchard (2004). *School reform from the inside out: Policy practice and performance*. Cambridge MA: Harvard Education Premier
- [21] Glover, E. (2007). Real principals listen. *Educational Leadership*, 65(1), 60-63.
- [22] Goleman, D., Boyatzis, R. & McKee, A. (2002). *Primal leadership: Realizing the power of emotional intelligence*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- [23] Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence*. New York, NY: Bantam Books.
- [24] Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ* (10th ed.). New York: Bantam Books.
- [25] Gragg, P. (2008). From theory to practice: Operation emotional intelligence. *Legal Reference Services Quarterly*, 27(2-3), 241-253.
- [26] Leban, W. V. (2003). The relationship between leader behavior and emotional intelligence of the project manager and the success of complex projects. Unpublished dissertation, Benedictine University.
- [27] Magda, Rod M. (2003). *The appropriate leadership styles and techniques in the 21st century*. The Modern Teacher.

- [28] Manzanero, Belen R. (2003). What it takes to be principal. *The Modern Teacher*.
- [29] McEvan, E. (2002). Seven steps to effective instructional leadership. California Crown Press, Inc.
- [30] Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. R. (2002). Mayer-Salovey-Caruso emotional intelligence test (MSCEIT). Toronto, Canada: Multi-Health Systems, Inc.
- [31] Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? In P. Salovey & D. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development and emotional intelligence: Implications for educators* (pp. 3-31). New York: Basic Books.
- [32] Mayer, J. D. & Salovey, P. (1995). Emotional intelligence and the construction and regulation of feelings. *Applied & Preventive Psychology*, 4, 197-208.
- [33] Mayer, J.D., & Salovey, P. (1993). The Intelligence of Emotional Intelligence. *Intelligence*, 17, 433-442.
- [34] Nelson, D. & Low, G. (2011). *Emotional intelligence: Achieving academic and career excellence* (2nd ed.). Boston, MA: Prentice Hall.
- [35] Palmer, B., & Stough, C. (2001). Workplace SUEIT: Swinburne University Emotional Intelligence Test - Descriptive report, Organisational Psychology Research Unit, Swinburne University, AU.
- [36] Perry, C., & Ball, I. (2005). Emotional intelligence and teaching: Further validation evidence. [Electronic version]. *Issues in Educational Research*, 15(2), 175-192.
- [37] Robbins, P., & Alvy, H. (2003). *The principal's companion*. Thousand Oaks, CA.: Corwin Press.
- [38] Schulte, M. J. (2003). Emotional intelligence: A predictive or descriptive construct in ascertaining leadership style or a new name for old knowledge? Unpublished dissertation, Our Lady of the Lake University.
- [39] Sergiovanni, T. (2000). *Leadership for school house*. San Francisco, Jossey-Bann
- [40] Singh, D. (2003). *Emotional intelligence at work: A professional guide*. New Delhi, India: Response Books.
- [41] Stefano, S., & Wasylshyn, K. (2005). Integrity, courage, empathy (ICE): Three leadership essentials. *HR. Human Resource Planning*, 28(4): 5-7.
- [42] Williams, H. W. (2004). Characteristics that distinguish outstanding urban principals: Emotional intelligence, problem-solving competencies, role perception and environmental adaptation. Unpublished dissertation, Case Western Reserve University.
- [43] Tan, Elsie A. (2014). *Instructional leadership of principals in the Division of Biliran*; Unpublished Masters Thesis: Naval State University.
- [44] Zapeda, S. (2003). *Instructional supervision: Applying tools and concepts*. New York. Eye on Education.
- [45] Angeles, Eduardo P. (2010). *Leadership – Key Element in Organizational Management*. *The Modern Teacher* Vol. 59.
- [46] Gosling, Bolden R and Manterano, J. and Denisson, P. (2003). A Review of Leadership Theory and Competency Frameworks.
- [47] Martires, C.R and Fule G.S (2000). *Management of Human Behavior*, Second Edition.
- [48] Leila G. Viduya (2000). *Leadership*. *The Modern Teacher* Vol. 50.
- [49] Aquino, Jonathan (2007). *Leadership in the Philippines Panorama*.
- [50] Desamito, Rosabel (2010). What it takes to be a Leader. *The Modern Teacher* Vol. 50.
- [51] Dela Cruz, John (2010). Five Salient Points to be considered by Leaders in Making Decisions. *The Modern Teacher* Vol. 50.
- [52] Waters, J. T., Marzano, R. J., & McNulty, B. A. (2003). *Balanced Leadership: What 30 years of research tells us about the effect of leadership on student achievement*. Aurora, CO: Mid-continent Research for Education and Learning, Retrieved July 16, 2004, from <http://www.mcrel.org>.
- [53] Weinberger, L. A. (2003). An examination of the relationship between emotional intelligence, leadership style and perceived leadership effectiveness . Unpublished dissertation. University of Minnesota
- [54] Zaccaro, S., Kemp, C., & Bader, P. (2003). Metacognitive skills on indices of leadership processes and performance. Retrieved November 26, 2003, from atgstg01.safepub.com/upm-data/5014